

An Interesting Case of Stable Pseudoaneurysm of Mitral-Aortic Intervalvular Fibrosa in A Young Man 5 Years After Bentall Procedure

Hadjivassiliou Sozomenos¹, Fragkou Vasileia², Trogkanis Efstratios^{3*}

¹American Medical Center, Nicosia, Cyprus

²University of Nicosia, Cyprus

³Department of Cardiology, General Hospital of Limassol, Cyprus

Citation: Hadjivassiliou Sozomenos, Fragkou Vasileia, Trogkanis Efstratios. An Interesting Case of Stable Pseudoaneurysm of Mitral-Aortic Intervalvular Fibrosa in A Young Man 5 Years After Bentall Procedure. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2025;4(3):1-5.

Received Date: 17 March, 2025; **Accepted Date:** 20 March, 2025; **Published Date:** 26 March, 2025

***Corresponding author:** Trogkanis Efstratios, Department of Cardiology, General Hospital of Limassol, Cyprus

Copyright: © Trogkanis Efstratios, Open Access 2025. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour(ICMCRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

INTRODUCTION/ABSTRACT

The mitral-aortic intervalvular fibrosa (MAIVF) is a fibrous structure located between the noncoronary cusp of the aortic valve and the anterior leaflet of the mitral valve.^[1,2] Superiorly, it is bounded by the pericardium and inferiorly it is adjacent to the left ventricular outflow tract (LVOT).^[2] Due to its relatively avascular nature, it has little resistance to infection and trauma which can result in weakening of the area and communication with the LVOT, forming a pseudoaneurysm of MAIVF (P-MAIVF).^[3]

The clinical presentation of P-MAIVF ranges from asymptomatic, in the absence of complications, to life-threatening entities such as coronary artery compression, fistulas and cardiac tamponade due to rupture.^[1,2,3] Early diagnosis and appropriate management and follow-up are crucial to reducing mortality risk.^[2]

CASE PRESENTATION

We present a 29-year-old fit man who had been diagnosed with bicuspid aortic valve as a child, with a Bentall procedure (aortic valve plus aortic root replacement) at the age of 26 years. After the surgery, he had a normal functional status and life according to his age.

He visited the Emergency Department of our hospital after a car accident because of a soft chest pain with myoskeletal features that responded to common analgesics. On a routine basis, we performed a transthoracic echocardiogram (TTE) that revealed a strong suspicion of P-MAIVF (**Image 1**) undiagnosed until that time, which was later confirmed by a transoesophageal echocardiogram (TOE) (**Image 2**) and a cardiac CT (cCT) (**Images 3 and 4**). Neither thrombus nor rupture were identified.

Looking back at the patient's electronic file, the first TTE exam performed 3 months post-surgery had similar findings as in the indexed patient's presentation. We repeated the TOE exam after one week of hospitalization with no changes in the characteristics of the pseudoaneurysm. After a multidisciplinary meeting with the heart team, it was advised to follow a conservative approach, as the patient has been asymptomatic for 3 years, with close and regular follow-up.

Image 1: TTE A4C view.

Image 2: TOE long axis view 113°.

Image 3: CT short axis.

Pseudoaneurysm at the left ventricle outflow tract (mitral-aortic intervalvular fibrosa)

Image 4: CT long-axis.

DISCUSSION

P-MAIVF is a rare, yet potentially severe condition that develops mainly as a result of endocarditis and surgical trauma.^[1] The most frequent traumatic operation is aortic valve replacement, however, other procedures such as ablation, cardiac catheterization and ventricular septal defect repair can also be associated with its formation.^[4] Other causes include direct chest trauma, congenital abnormality and severe aortic regurgitation.^[3] In our case, the patient had a history of Bentall procedure two years ago. The pathogenesis is still unclear. A hypothesis is that the surgical suture anchoring the aortic valve prosthesis to the fibrous ring causes traction on the vulnerable MAIVF, leading to dehiscence of the area; over time, the fibrous tissue is stretched and that results in a pseudoaneurysm.^[5]

P-MAIVFs are usually asymptomatic. Clinical manifestations develop as a result of complications.^[1] The most frequent presentations are signs and symptoms of infective endocarditis, followed by dyspnoea and heart failure, angina due to compression of a coronary artery, and cerebrovascular events as a result of clots in the pseudoaneurysm cavity.^[3,4] Fistula formation between the LVOT and the left atrium or the aorta and pseudoaneurysm rupture in the pericardium leading to cardiac tamponade constitute two rarer but dreaded complications.^[1,6] Our patient was asymptomatic and the P-MAIVF was incidentally discovered on routine imaging.

Due to the limited number of P-MAIVF cases, the natural history and prognosis of the condition is uncertain and thus, the appropriate management is debatable.^[2,5] In fear of fatal complications, surgery is currently the cornerstone treatment for P-MAIVF.^[1,6] However, the corrective (re-do) surgical procedures are associated with high morbidity and mortality.^[7] Consequently, an increasing number of authors suggest a conservative approach with frequent follow-ups, every 6-12 months, as an alternative in patients with high post-operative risk and those without perilous features, namely active endocarditis, complications, or P-MAIVF > 3cm.^[2,5,6,7,8,9,10] Grimaldi et al. argue that categorization of patients into those with or without endocarditis and according to symptoms may be helpful in clinical decision-making. Based on our patient's history of a previous Bentall

procedure and his asymptomatic presentation after 3 years of that complication, it was decided to be managed conservatively with watchful surveillance. Today, 2 more years after the patient's first presentation to our hospital and 5 years in total after the establishment of that complication, the patient remains in a good functional status with no cardiovascular events.

CONCLUSION

P-MAIVF is a rare complication of endocarditis and aortic valve replacement surgery with a broad spectrum of clinical manifestations from clinically silent to life-threatening situations. Due to its rarity, the course and the prognosis of the condition are still unclear and therefore, the treatment approach remains controversial. Because in most cases of P-MAIVF early surgery is a choice to avoid further enlargement and prevent life-threatening complications, there is a sparse number of reports on nonsurgical management with more than 1 year follow-up. Here, we presented the case of a patient who remains asymptomatic without changes in the size of P-MAIVF or presentation of complications in a 5-year-long follow-up, which, we hope, will contribute to the existing knowledge for the better evaluation and management of such patients.

REFERENCES

1. Şahan E, Gül M, Şahan S, Sokmen E, Guray Y, Tufekçioğlu O. Pseudoaneurysm of the mitral–aortic intervalvular fibrosa. Herz. 2014;40(S2):182-189.
2. Han J, He Y, Gu X, Sun L, Zhao Y, Liu W, et al. Echocardiographic Diagnosis and Outcome of Pseudoaneurysm of the Mitral-Aortic Intervalvular Fibrosa. Medicine. 2016;95(11):e3116.
3. Xie M, Li Y, Cheng T, Wang X, Lu Q, He L et al. Pseudoaneurysm of the mitral-aortic intervalvular fibrosa. International Journal of Cardiology. 2013;166(1):2-7.
4. Apostolidou E, Beale C, Poppas A, Stockwell P. Pseudoaneurysm of the Mitral-Aortic Intervalvular Fibrosa: A Case Series with Literature Review. CASE. 2017;1(6):221-226.
5. Grimaldi A, Ho S, Pozzoli A, Sora N, Taramasso M, Benussi S et al. Pseudoaneurysm of mitral-aortic intervalvular fibrosa. Interactive CardioVascular and Thoracic Surgery. 2011;13(2):142-147.
6. Sudhakar S, Sewani A, Agrawal M, Uretsky B. Pseudoaneurysm of the Mitral-Aortic Intervalvular Fibrosa (MAIVF): A Comprehensive Review. Journal of the American Society of Echocardiography. 2010;23(10):1009-1018.
7. Gin A, Hong H, Rosenblatt A, Black M, Ristow B, Popper R. Pseudoaneurysms of the mitral-aortic intervalvular fibrosa: Survival without reoperation. American Heart Journal. 2011;161(1):130.e1-130.e5.
8. Varga A, Tilea I, Tatar C, Iancu D, Jiga M, Dumbrava R et al. Native Aortic Valve Endocarditis Complicated by Splenic Infarction and Giant Mitral-Aortic Intervalvular Fibrosa Pseudoaneurysm—A Case Report and Brief Review of the Literature. Diagnostics. 2021;11(2):251.
9. Hasin T, Reisner S, Agmon Y. Large pseudoaneurysms of the mitral-aortic intervalvular fibrosa: long-term natural history without surgery in two patients. European Heart Journal - Cardiovascular Imaging. 2011;12(3):E24-E24.

10. Boi A, Garau G, Rossi A, Lixi G, Armandi L, Fele G et al. Mitro-aortic fibrosa pseudoaneurysm and concomitant aortic stenosis: How to kill two birds with a stone. Journal of Cardiac Surgery. 2020;35(9):2414-2417.